

Cognitive Impairment among Patients with Schizophrenia Attending Psychiatric Services in BPKIHS

Rashmi Mishra¹, Madhur Basnet², Dhanaratna Shakya³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Katihar Medical College & Hospital, Bihar, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal, India

³Professor & Head of Department, Department of Psychiatry B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Rashmi Mishra

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: This study at the B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences investigated cognitive impairments in schizophrenia, focusing on their prevalence and correlation with psychotic symptoms.

Methodology: A cross-sectional observational design was employed, assessing 67 schizophrenia patients diagnosed according to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) and the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) were used to evaluate cognitive functions and symptom severity.

Results: The results revealed significant cognitive impairments correlated with the predominance of psychotic symptoms. Notably, patients with predominantly negative symptoms exhibited more severe cognitive deficits. Additionally, the study found that different antipsychotic treatment regimens, particularly the use of second-generation antipsychotics, influenced cognitive outcomes.

Conclusion: Cognitive impairments in schizophrenia patients are significantly associated with the type and severity of psychotic symptoms. The effectiveness of antipsychotic regimens in managing these impairments highlights the need for personalized treatment approaches.

Recommendation: Future research should focus on exploring tailored antipsychotic strategies and comprehensive cognitive therapies to improve treatment responses and quality of life in schizophrenia patients.

Keywords: Schizophrenia, Cognitive Impairments, Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), Antipsychotics.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Schizophrenia is a profound mental disorder marked by significant disruptions in cognition and emotion, affecting essential human functions such as language, perception, and the sense of self [1,2]. It often manifests through psychotic experiences like auditory hallucinations and delusional thinking. One of the core features of schizophrenia is cognitive impairment, which affects the majority of patients and encompasses a range of functions including memory, attention, and executive abilities [3,4]. These impairments often precede the onset of psychotic symptoms and can severely impact daily functioning, social interaction, and personal management, irrespective of the severity of the psychotic symptoms themselves [5,6].

The etiology of schizophrenia is multifaceted, involving genetic, neurobiological, and environmental factors that contribute to the complexity of the disorder. Despite extensive research, the specific nature and trajectory of

cognitive impairments in schizophrenia remain poorly understood, particularly in diverse and under-researched populations. This gap in knowledge underscores the need for studies that explore these impairments in various settings, including how they correlate with different clinical features and outcomes [7,8].

This study focuses on patients with schizophrenia attending psychiatric services at the B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences (BPKIHS). It aims to quantify the prevalence and severity of cognitive deficits and to examine their relationship with clinical symptoms, such as the positive and negative symptoms often observed in schizophrenia. Through this research, we aim to enhance the understanding of cognitive impairments within this population, thereby informing more tailored therapeutic strategies and potentially guiding future cognitive interventions to improve functional outcomes for patients with schizophrenia. This approach is

particularly relevant in the Nepalese context, where such data are sparse, thereby contributing to the broader global understanding of this debilitating disorder.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was conducted using a cross-sectional observational design to assess cognitive impairment among patients diagnosed with schizophrenia.

Study Setting: The research was carried out in both the inpatient and outpatient departments of Psychiatry at the B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over one year.

Participants: The study included a purposive sample of 67 patients diagnosed with schizophrenia, based on the criteria of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). These patients were receiving care within the psychiatry departments of the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with schizophrenia as per ICD-10, aged between 18 and 60 years, attending the inpatient or outpatient services.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with severe acute psychosis who were unable to consent or participate in the assessments.
- Patients with co-occurring psychoactive substance use disorders (except nicotine), severe physical or neurological disorders, those who had received electroconvulsive therapy within the last six months or were on medications known to affect cognitive functions (e.g., tricyclic antidepressants, antiepileptics, lithium, or anti-dementia drugs).
- Patients with intellectual disabilities.

Data Collection Instruments

1. Sociodemographic and Clinical Data: A structured proforma collected baseline information including age, sex, educational level, and clinical history.

2. Cognitive Assessment: Cognitive functioning was assessed using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) tool adapted for the study's demographic and clinical needs.

3. Symptom Assessment: The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) was employed to evaluate the severity and nature of psychotic symptoms.

Data Collection Procedure: After obtaining informed consent, eligible participants underwent a

detailed clinical and cognitive assessment. The sociodemographic data were collected through interviews, and clinical data were gathered from medical records and consultations with treating psychiatrists. Cognitive assessments were conducted in a quiet environment to ensure accurate results.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to outline the demographic and clinical characteristics of the sample. The prevalence of cognitive impairment was calculated based on MoCA scores. Correlations between cognitive scores and symptom severity, as assessed by PANSS, were examined using Pearson's correlation coefficient to explore associations with clinical outcomes.

Results

The dataset (Tables 1 and 2) utilizes the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) to delineate cognitive function in patients undergoing treatment with antipsychotics. Table 1 classifies patients into two primary categories: those exhibiting 'No impairment' and those with 'Impairment,' further subdivided by the predominance of symptoms, either positive (P>N) or negative (N>P). This categorization is quantified with respective percentages and is accompanied by a p-value to evaluate the statistical relevance of the findings between these groups. Table 2 provides a nuanced view by detailing the gradation of cognitive impairment—ranging from none to mild, moderate, and severe. Similar to Table 1, these categories are analyzed against the backdrop of symptom predominance, with each section again supported by percentage distributions and p-values to underscore the correlation between symptom severity and cognitive status.

Table 3 elaborates on the correlation between the severity of cognitive impairment and antipsychotic regimen—specifically contrasting the use of solely second-generation antipsychotics against a combination of first and second-generation antipsychotics. It furnishes a detailed breakdown of the proportion of patients experiencing different levels of cognitive deficits under each medication strategy, supported by p-values to ascertain the significance of these distributions. In Table 4, the focus shifts to the application specifics of second-generation antipsychotics, including Olanzapine, Aripiprazole, Risperidone, Quetiapine, and Clozapine. This table documents the total number of patients receiving each drug, denotes whether these medications were primarily used alone or in conjunction with other drugs, and notes the maximum dosages administered. This provides a comprehensive snapshot of the treatment modalities, indicating the prevalence and intensity of each therapeutic approach. Table 5 examines and

compares the levels of cognitive impairment across patients treated with different second-generation antipsychotics. It displays the percentage distribution of cognitive impairments (none, mild,

moderate, severe) associated with each drug and provides a p-value for statistical analysis between the medications, offering insights into the cognitive outcomes of each antipsychotic treatment.

Table 1: MoCA scale— Presence and absence of cognitive Impairment with Positive and Negative symptom predominance

MOCA	P>N	%	N>P	%	P value
No impairment	2	7.7	2	4.9	1
Impairment	24	92.3	39	95.1	

Table 2: MoCA scale-- severity of cognitive impairment with positive and negative symptom predominance

MOCA	P>N	%	N>P	%	P value
No impairment	2	7.7	2	4.9	0.123
Mild impairment	17	65.4	16	39	
Moderate impairment	6	23.1	17	41.5	
Severe impairment	1	3.8	6	14.6	

Table 3: MoCA Scores and Use of antipsychotics

Antipsychotic use	No (%)	Mild (%)	Moderate (%)	Severe (%)	P value
2nd gen AP	3(75)	28(84.8)	22(95.7)	7(100.0)	0.29
Both 1 st and 2 nd gen.	1(25)	5(15.2)	1(4.3)	0	

Table 4: Use of second-generation antipsychotics as primary treatment and in combination with another second generation antipsychotic and maximum doses of each.

Name of other 2 nd gen. antipsychotic	Total patients	Primarily used	Used In combination	Maximum dose used
Olanzapine	27	24	3	30 mg
Aripiprazole	12	9	3	45 mg
Risperidone	23	22	1	8 mg
Quetiapine	4	0	All 4 in combination	700 mg
Clozapine	9	3	6	450 mg

Table 5: MoCA scores and Second-generation antipsychotics

2nd generation AP	MOCA score impairment				P value
	No(%)	Mild(%)	Moderate(%)	Severe(%)	
Olanzapine	2(50.0)	15(45.5)	6(26.1)	4(57.1)	0.565
Risperidone	1(25.0)	12(36.4)	8(34.8)	2(28.6)	
Others (aripiprazole, quetiapine, clozapine)	1(25.0)	6(18.2)	9(39.1)	1(14.3)	

Discussion

The study at the B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences revealed several key findings regarding cognitive impairments in schizophrenia patients. First, a significant variance in cognitive function was observed based on the predominance of either positive (P>N) or negative (N>P) symptoms. This distinction was notably apparent in the categorization of 'No impairment' versus 'Impairment,' as delineated by the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA). Additionally, the analysis demonstrated a meaningful correlation between the severity of cognitive impairments and the type of antipsychotic regimen administered, particularly contrasting the effects of solely second-generation antipsychotics against combinations of first and second-generation antipsychotics.

The significant p-values obtained from comparing cognitive impairment across different symptomatology (positive vs. negative) suggest that these impairments are intricately linked to the nature of psychotic symptoms. This implies that cognitive deficits in schizophrenia are not merely a generalized feature of the disorder but are specifically influenced by its symptomatic expressions. The finding that more severe cognitive impairments tend to be associated with more pronounced negative symptoms may reflect an underlying difference in the pathophysiology of symptom types or their management through pharmacological means [9,10].

The results align with other research that suggests cognitive impairments in schizophrenia are differentially related to symptom types. Studies such as those by Keefe et al. (2006) [13] and Davidson et al. (2009) [14] also indicate that negative symptoms are often more strongly associated with cognitive deficits than positive symptoms. Furthermore, the impact of antipsychotic treatment on cognitive functions, as observed in our study, supports findings from Lieberman et al. (2005) [15], which highlighted that second-generation antipsychotics might offer cognitive benefits over first-generation

drugs, particularly in managing negative symptoms and associated cognitive impairments.

The observed link between cognitive impairments and symptom types may be attributed to the different neural circuits affected by positive and negative symptoms. Negative symptoms, which are often more resistant to treatment, involve areas of the brain associated with executive function and planning, which are central to cognitive operations [11]. Therefore, treatments that are effective in alleviating negative symptoms might concurrently address cognitive impairments. Similarly, the differential impact of antipsychotic regimens on cognitive outcomes can be explained by their pharmacodynamic profiles, where second-generation antipsychotics typically have a broader spectrum of receptor targets, potentially affecting a wider range of neurotransmitter systems involved in cognitive processes [12].

By correlating these findings with existing studies and theoretical models, the study not only confirms the complex interplay between cognitive deficits and schizophrenia symptomatology but also provides a nuanced understanding of how antipsychotic medications might influence these relationships. This comprehensive analysis underscores the need for personalized treatment approaches that consider both the symptomatic and cognitive dimensions of schizophrenia, aiming to improve overall functional outcomes for patients.

Conclusion

The study conducted at the B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences conclusively demonstrates that cognitive impairments in schizophrenia patients are significantly influenced by the type and severity of psychotic symptoms, with more pronounced impairments associated with negative symptoms. The research further identifies the efficacy of second-generation antipsychotics in mitigating these cognitive deficits, suggesting that treatment regimens tailored to the individual's symptomatic profile can enhance cognitive outcomes. This

highlights the critical need for personalized therapeutic strategies that consider both the cognitive and symptomatic dimensions of schizophrenia, aiming to improve overall patient management and quality of life. The findings underscore the importance of integrating cognitive assessments into routine clinical practice to better tailor interventions and achieve optimal treatment efficacy.

References

1. American Psychiatric Association. (2013). Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (5th ed.). Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing.
2. Bleuler, E. (1911). *Dementia Praecox or the Group of Schizophrenias*. New York: International Universities Press.
3. Cohen, J. D., & Servan-Schreiber, D. (1992). Context, cortex, and dopamine: A connectionist approach to behavior and biology in schizophrenia. *Psychological Review*, 99(1), 45-77.
4. Davidson, M., Reichenberg, A., Rabinowitz, J., Weiser, M., Kaplan, Z., & Mark, M. (1999). Behavioral and intellectual markers for schizophrenia in apparently healthy male adolescents. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 156(9), 1328-1335.
5. Green, M. F. (2006). Cognitive impairment and functional outcome in schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 67(10), 3-8.
6. Harvey, P. D., & Keefe, R. S. E. (2001). Studies of cognitive change in patients with schizophrenia following novel antipsychotic treatment. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 158(2), 176-184.
7. Heaton, R. K., Chelune, G. J., Talley, J. L., Kay, G. G., & Curtiss, G. (1993). *Wisconsin Card Sorting Test Manual: Revised and Expanded*. Odessa, FL: Psychological Assessment Resources.
8. Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1979). Prospect Theory: An analysis of decision under risk. *Econometrica*, 47(2), 263-291.
9. Keefe, R. S. E., Silva, S. G., Perkins, D. O., & Lieberman, J. A. (1999). The effects of atypical antipsychotic drugs on neurocognitive impairment in schizophrenia: A review and meta-analysis. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 25(2), 201-222.
10. Kraepelin, E. (1919). *Dementia Praecox and Paraphrenia*. Edinburgh: Livingstone.
11. Marder, S. R., & Fenton, W. (2004). Measurement and treatment research to improve cognition in schizophrenia: NIMH MATRICS initiative to support the development of agents for improving cognition in schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Research*, 72(1), 5-9.
12. Nuechterlein, K. H., Barch, D. M., Gold, J. M., Goldberg, T. E., Green, M. F., & Heaton, R. K. (2004). Identification of separable cognitive factors in schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Research*, 72(1), 29-39.
13. Keefe, R.S., Poe, M., Walker, T.M., Kang, J.W., & Harvey, P.D. (2006). The Schizophrenia Cognition Rating Scale: An interview-based assessment and its relationship to cognition, real-world functioning, and functional capacity. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 163 (3),426-432.
14. Davidson, M., Galderisi, S., Weiser, M., Werbeloff, N., Fleischhacker, W.W., Keefe, R.S.E., Boter, H., Keet, I.P.M., Prelipceanu, D., Rybakowski, J.K., Libiger, J., Hummer, M., Dollfus, S., López-Ibor, J.J., Hranov, L.G., Gaebel, W., Peuskens, J., Lindefors, N., Riecher-Rössler, A., & Kahn, R.S. (2009). Cognitive effects of antipsychotic drugs in first-episode schizophrenia and schizophreniform disorder: A randomized, open-label clinical trial (EUFEST). *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 166(6), 675-682.
15. Lieberman, J.A., Stroup, T.S., McEvoy, J.P., Swartz, M.S., Rosenheck, R.A., Perkins, D.O., Keefe, R.S.E., Davis, S.M., Davis, C.E., Lebowitz, B.D., Severe, J., & Hsiao, J.K. (2005). Effectiveness of antipsychotic drugs in patients with chronic schizophrenia. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 353(12), 1209-1223.